

Research Article

Empirical Validation of the “G-d’s Physics’ Critical Prediction Resolves the “Gravitational Enigma”!

Jehonathan Bentovish

Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

*Corresponding author

Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich), Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

Received: 06 Aug 2023

Accepted : 10 Aug 2023

Published: 20 Aug 2023

Copyright

© 2023 Jehonathan Bentovish

OPEN ACCESS

Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm based on a “time-sensitive” measurement of a predicted increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days’ time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish’s e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

The “Gravitational Enigma” (GE) relates to four different “facets” representing “unexplained” elements within the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm of General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) that are somehow associated with the phenomenon of the “Gravitational Force”, including: a) unification of GRT & QM. b) a satisfactory explanation for the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion. c) unification of the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the “curvature of Space-Time”. This GE is shown to be resolved based on the discovery of a New “G-d’s Physics” (G-D’S PHYSICS) and the direct empirical validation of one of its unique “Critical Predictions”.

Introduction

Perhaps the key unresolved “enigma” in Twenty-First Century’s Theoretical Physics is the “Gravitational Enigma” (GE), i.e.: *Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of “gravitation” which can: a) Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical “Dark-Matter” (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the “curvature of Space-Time” by “massive objects” (e.g., based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’ New Scientific “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm);* Thus far, the “Gravitational Force” has been explained based on GRT’s key assumption wherein this “Gravitational Force” (GF) is responsible for the “curvature of Space-Time” – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying “nature”. Moreover, this assumed GF remains “inexplicable” (and “independent”) of the Standard Model’s proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles’ interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved “Gravitational Enigma”?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this “Gravitational Enigma” (GE) based on the discovery of a New “G-d’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm [1-30].

The potential capacity of this New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this “Gravitational Enigma” (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ”), thereby pro-

ducing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”! Additionally, the UCP’s simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF’s frame/s yields the UCP’s novel “computational definitions” of the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time” (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two “Computational Dimensions” of “Framework” and “Consistency! According to this (new) G-D’S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the “mass” value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those “Framework” (e.g., “frame” or “object”) and “Consistency” (“consistent” or “inconsistent”) “Computational Dimensions”: Such that the UCP computes “Framework” – “consistent” vs. “inconsistent” computations, as the “space” and “energy” values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF’s); and “Object” – “consistent” or “inconsistent” computations, as the “mass” and “time” values (across a given UF’s series) (Figure 1):

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	“Space”	“Mass”
Inconsistent	“Energy”	“Time”

FIGURE 1: UCP’S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Intriguingly, these novel “G-D’S PHYSICS” UCP’s “computational definitions” of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an “Universal Computational Formula” (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational “by-products” of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} = \begin{matrix} s * e \\ t * m \end{matrix}$$

UF's {n...n...n} [Px1 (a...z)]

FIGURE 2. The “UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA” (UCF)

Note: which is accompanied by “G-D’S PHYSICS” computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time”.

The UCF’s Relativistic Format:

UCP’s Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. “ST” Points	1	2+	All Points

in which GRT’s (famous) “Energy-Mass Equivalence” is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF’s Quantum Format

$$\left. \begin{matrix} e * s = m * c^2 \\ \hline t \quad h \end{matrix} \right\}$$

in which “Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle’s” (“complimentary pairs”)

are embedded as “special cases” within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of “G-D’S PHYSICS” or G-D’S PHYSICS).

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm’s potential resolution of the GE’s first component – i.e., a) Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of “gravitation” which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); is given through this (singular higher-ordered) UCP’s (in-depth) analysis of the (true) “computational basis” of the “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D’S PHYSICS’s computational analysis, this “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from GRT’s strict “Speed of Light Barrier” for the transmission of any “signal” (or even “information”) across “space” and “time” – which seems to be “contradicted” by QM’s “Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon”, indicating that the measurement of one “entangled particle” “instantaneously” affects the “complimentary” (“space/energy” or “mass/time”) measurement of the other “entangled particle”?! But, according to the new CUT’s Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and “resolution”- of this apparent “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from the UCP’s singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all “Single Spatial-Temporal” computation (“SST”): “particle” of relativistic “object” (e.g., relating to only “one” spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), “Multi Spatial-Temporal” computation (MST): “wave” (e.g., relating to at least “two” points being measured at any point in time) or “Exhaustive Spatial Temporal” (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all “exhaustive” spatial pixels comprising an entire “Universal Frame”, UF), across a series of UF’s frames (Figure 3);

UCP’s Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. “ST” Points	1	2+	All Points

FIGURE 3: UCP’S “SST”, “MST” & “EST” COMPUTATIONS

In order to advance towards demonstrating in what manner can this New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm address and resolve the “second” (abovementioned) facet of the GE, we must now validate a unique “Critical Prediction” of this New G-D’S PHYSICS – as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying GRT & QM!

METHOD & RESULTS

In order to directly contrast between the new “G-D’S PHYSICS” Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, the “G-D’S PHYSICS” identified a unique “Critical-Prediction” relating to the “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE) due to the “Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis” (CHCFH) associated with the two days’ “Rosh-Hashana” (New Year’s) time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCP; According to the Old (“Material-Causal”) GRT’s Paradigm, the (purely hypothetical concept of) DM predicts a “constant-rate” of the universe’s expansion – i.e., which should not increase over time! In contrast, according to one of the new Theoretical Postulates of the “G-D’S PHYSICS” termed: The “Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis” (CHCFH), whenever there is a “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF), e.g., of a large group of human-beings focusing upon this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP), this results in an “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (“UNCIARE”)! For example, during the Jewish “Rosh-Hashana’s” (new year) two days’ special time-interval, according to the “G-D’S PHYSICS” (unique) “UNCIARE” “Critical Prediction”, there should be measured a “non-continuous increase” in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion (which should “carry over” throughout the whole new year!) Indeed, an (indirect) empirical validation of this “G-D’S PHYSICS” “UNCIARE”

“Critical Prediction” was already given based on the (otherwise) “unexplained” findings regarding the “Universe’s Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap” (UACAREG)! Empirically, a basic (unexplained) “gap” exists between the universe’s measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe’s (contemporary) rate of expansion[32,33,35]. This “Universe’s Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap” (UACAREG) negates the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” which predicts a “constant rate” of the universe’s expansion?! Therefore, the abovementioned UNCIARE results (unequivocally) validate and support a unique “Critical Predictions” of the New “G-D’S PHYSICS” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM!

DISCUSSION

Based on the clear empirical validations of this unique Critical Prediction of “G-D’S PHYSICS” as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein G-D’S PHYSICS is recognized as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics! Based upon Thomas Kuhn’s [31]. (well-known) analysis of occurrence of “Paradigmatic-Shifts” (in any particular scientific discipline), the acceptance of the New G-D’S PHYSICS as the New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm may be equivalent to the acceptance of Einstein’s GRT as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twentieth Century Physics – also based on such an empirical validation of a unique “Critical Prediction” associated with GRT (e.g., Mercury’s “double-valued” perihelion pathway around the Sun due to the curvature of “Space-Time” by the Sun’s mass etc.).

As such, the New G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm completely unifies between these four basic physical features (of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time”) – e.g., for the first time in Theoretical Physics, since Einstein’s GRT was able to unify only between “space” and “energy” as “a four dimensional “Space-Time” continuum, and between “energy” and “mass” through the famous “Energy-Mass Equivalence”, and connect between certain “massive objects” as “curving Space-Time”; but not yet (completely) integrate these four basic physical features within a singular UCP! Indeed, this complete unification of those four basic physical features as secondary computational “by-products” of the same singular UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe) offer us an alternative conceptualization of the manner in which this singular UCP completely integrates the Four Forces: This is because these Four Forces – Weak and Strong Nuclear Forces, the Electromagnetic Force and the Gravitational Force all represent different aspects of this singular UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features, which are all integrated by the G-D’S PHYSICS’s New “Universal Computational Formula”!

Specifically, the UCP re-explains the “Gravitational Force” as merely representing its differential computation of relatively “High-Mass; Low energy” (HMLE) vs. “low-mass; high-energy” (LMHE) objects (particles): According to the New G-D’S PHYSICS, it is suggested that the UCP “differentially computes” the HMLE particles as occupying relatively “stable regions” within each consecutive UF’s frame/s, whereas those LMHE particles seem to “alternate” their “spatial position” (across the series of UF’s frames), they creating “unstable regions” (within those UF’s frames’ series)!? Hence, what “appears” as a “curvature of Space-Time” around “massive objects” (HMLE) – (truly) only represents the UCP’s “differential computation” of those HMLE “stable regions” of the UF’s which are surrounded by the relatively “less stable regions” (LMHE)! Indeed, an indirect empirical support for this New G-D’S PHYSICS’s “alternative explanation” for the “Gravitational Force” was also given (in this article) through its unique “Critical Prediction” confirmation given through the “Proton Radius Puzzle” findings [41-43], indicating that based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’s

ICS’s computational definition of “mass” as an “Object-consistent” measure, the relatively “more-massive” Muon (negatively charged) particle (which “sinks” into the Proton of the “Muon-replaced Hydrogen Atom”) “causing” it to become more “spatially-consistent” than the equivalent “Standard Hydrogen Proton” (which is not “conjoined” with the “lighter electron” particle)! These “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings failed to be explained based on the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying QM (and GRT; e.g., despite various attempts to explain this “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings: the “three-body force”[40], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction[38,39], higher dimension gravity [44], a new boson[45])! In other words, the G-D’S PHYSICS’s new “computational definitions” of the manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) UCP computes the “mass” of any given particle (such as the “more massive” Muon particle, relatively to a “less massive” particle (such as the “electron”) perfectly explains the significant reduction in the Hydrogen’s Proton Radius (e.g., “spatial consistency”), when surrounded by the Muon as opposed to when surrounded by the electron!

Therefore, the G-D’S PHYSICS’s discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features, alongside its novel “computational definitions” for each of those physical features – elegantly resolves the four different “facets” of the GE: a) Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) – based on the UCP’s simultaneous computation of SST “particles” as embedded within “MST-wave” computation (thereby resolving the apparent contradiction between the “Speed of Light Barrier” and the “quantum entanglement” phenomenon); b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion (that is not based on the purely hypothetical “Dark-Matter” (DM) concept) – based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’s stipulated and empirically validated “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE), associated with the G-D’S PHYSICS’s newly discovered UCP and its connection with a “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (at “special time intervals” such as the JRH two days’ time interval); c) Unify between the “Gravitational Force” and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force! – based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’s newly discovered UCF, and associated novel UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features. d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the “curvature of Space-Time” by “massive objects” (based on the G-D’S PHYSICS’s New Scientific “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm) – based on the UCP’s “differential computation” of relatively “stable regions” of “HMLE objects” surrounded by relatively “less stable regions” of “LMHE regions” (pointing at the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features)! Indeed, the potential significance (and “beauty”) of the G-D’S PHYSICS’s (novel) resolution of the GE stems not only from its broad “relevance” to such “diverse facets” (of the GE) as the unification of the (macroscopic) GRT & (subatomic) QM realms, the unification of the Four Forces, offering an alternative (exciting) explanations for the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion (while “discarding” DM as “superfluous”, i.e., “non-existent”!) and the “curvature of Space-Time” (based on the UCP’s differential computation of HMLE vs. LMHE); but perhaps even more significantly in offering 21st century Theoretical Physics a new “A-Causal Computation” G-D’S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm that is able to completely unify the four basic physical features within a singular (novel) “Universal Computational Formula” based on the major discovery of the singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features!

REFERENCES

1. Bentwich, J. (2012a) “Harmonizing Quantum Mechanics and Relativity Theory”. Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, Intech (ISBN 979-953-307-377-3), Chapter 22: 515-550.

2. Bentwich, J. (2012b) "Theoretical Validation of the G-d's Physics". Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, (ISBN 979-953-307-3773), Chapter 23: 551-598.
3. Bentwich, J. (2013b). "The Theoretical Ramifications of the G-d's Physics". Advances in Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7), Chapter 28: 671-882.
4. Bentwich, J. (2015). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics): A Candidate 'Theory of Everything'. Selected Topics in Application of Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-2126-8) Chapter 6.
5. Bentwich, J. (2016) 'G-d's Physics': A Paradigmatic Shift. Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure & Applied Physics.
6. Bentwich, J. (2017b) The G-d's Physics: Explaining the Universe from "Without". SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
7. Bentwich, J. (2017c). The G-d's Physics: A New 'A-Causal Computation' Physics. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
8. Bentwich, J. (2017d). The 'G-d's Physics' (G-d's Physics) May Challenge the 'Big-Bang Theory'. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
9. Bentwich, J. (2017f). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics): Time "Reversal" May be Possible. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
10. Bentwich, J. (2017g). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics) Transcends Relativity's Speed of Light Constraint. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics, Special Issue.
11. Bentwich, J. (2017h). The G-d's Physics's New Physics: Transcending Space, Time and Causality. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
12. Bentwich, J. (2017i). A "Supra-Spatial-Temporal Universal Consciousness Reality". Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure & Applied Physics, Special Issue: The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics)- A Paradigmatic Shift in 21st Century Physics.
13. Bentwich, J. (2017j). A New Science: An Infinite Omniscient Dynamic-Equilibrium Universal Consciousness Reality. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
14. Bentwich, J. (2017k). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics) Challenges Darwin's 'Natural Selection Principle'! SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
15. Bentwich, J. (2017l). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics) Challenges the Second Law of Thermodynamics. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
16. Bentwich, J. (2017m). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics): An Empirical & Mathematical Validation of the 'G-d's Physics'; SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
17. Bentwich, J. (2017n). The G-d's Physics (G-Ds Physics) New Science; SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
18. Bentwich, J. (2018b). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics): What is "Time"? The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18: 8-A.
19. Bentwich, J. (2018c). The Universal Consciousness Reality's Camouflage: The Physical Universe! The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18: 8-A.
20. Bentwich, J. (2018d). The G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics) Epilogue: Can Human Consciousness Affect the Cosmos? The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18: 8-A.
21. Bentwich, J. (2019c). A Call for Cosmologists & Experimental Physicists: Empirical Validation of the 'G-d's Physics' (G-d's Physics) New Paradigm through "Time-Sensitive" Astronomical and Subatomic Measurements. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19: 6.
22. Bentwich, J. (2019d). The 'G-d's Physics' (G-d's Physics): Redefining Mass, Gravity & the Physical Universe. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19: 6.
23. Bentwich, J. (2019d). Astronomical Validation of the G-d's Physics (G-d's Physics) "Critical Prediction" & Resolution of the "Universe's Accelerated Expansion Rate Enigma" (UAERE). The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, 19: 6.
24. Bentwich, J. (2019e) Urgent Call for Empirical Validation of the G-d's Physics's (G-d's Physics) New 21st Century 'A-Causal Computation' (ACC) Paradigm. Acta Scientific Applied Physics, Volume 1: 1.
25. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2020b). An Urgent Need for "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm's Empirical Validation. Advances in Theoretical & Computational Physics. Volume 32: 59-65.
26. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021). "G-d's Physics": A New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century. iUniverse. ISBN 9781532090370.
27. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021c). "G-d's Physics": On the True Nature of "Dark-Energy" & "Dark-Matter". In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
28. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021g). "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm: A Complete Integration of "Space" & "Energy", "Mass" & "Time"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
29. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021h). "G-d's Physics": Complete Unification of the Four Basic Forces of Nature & "Geulah"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
30. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021i). Fulfilling Einstein's Quest: "G-d's Physics" New Twenty-First Century's Paradigm's Multi-Level Computational Universe. In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
31. Kuhn, Thomas S. (1962). The Structure of Scientific Revolutions (1st ed.). University of Chicago Press. pp. 172. LCCN 62019621
32. Riess A. G., Casertano S., Yuan W. et al (2018a). Is there any measurable redshift dependence on the SN Ia absolute magnitude? ApJ 861 126
33. Shajib A. J., Birrer S., Treu T. et al (2020). STRIDES: a 3.9 per cent measurement of the Hubble constant from the strong lens system DES J0408-5354. MNRAS 494 6072
34. Scolnic D., Rest A., Riess A. et al (2014). Systematic Uncertainties Associated with the Cosmological Analysis of the First PAN-STARRS1 Type Ia Supernova Sample. ApJ 795 45
35. Wong K. C., Suyu S. H., Chen G. C. F. et al (2020). H0LiCOW - XIII. A 2.4 per cent measurement of H0 from lensed quasars: 5.3σ tension between early- and late- Universe probes. MNRAS 498 1420
36. Bolton, J.S., Caputo, A., Liu, M. & Viel, M. (2022). Comparison of Low-Redshift Lyman-α Forest Observations to Hydrodynamical Simulations with Dark Photon Dark Matter. DOI 10.1103/PhysRevLett.129.21110.
37. Moskowicz, C. (2021). Dark Matter's Last Stand. Scientific American 324, 4, 64-71 (April 2021) doi:10.1038/scientificamerican0421-64
38. Onofrio, R. (2013). "Proton radius puzzle and quantum gravity at the Fermi scale". EPL. 104 (2): 20002. arXiv:1312.3469. Bibcode:2013EL....10420002O. doi:10.1209/0295-5075/104/20002. S2CID 119243594
39. Zyga, Lisa (November 26, 2013). "Proton radius puzzle may be solved by quantum gravity". Phys.org. Retrieved September 2, 2016.
40. Karr, J.; Hilico, L. (2012). "Why three-body physics does not solve the proton-radius puzzle". Physical Review Letters. 109 (10): 103401. arXiv:1205.0633. Bibcode:2012PhRvL.109j3401K. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.109.103401. PMID 23005286. S2CID 12752418
41. Pohl R, Antognini A, Nez F, Amaro FD, Biraben F, et al. (July 2010). "The size of the proton" (PDF). Nature. 466 (7303): 213-216. Bibcode:2010Natur. 466..213P. doi:10.1038/nature09250. PMID

20613837. S2CID 4424731.

42. Pohl R, et al. (2016a). "Laser spectroscopy of muonic deuterium". *Science*. 353 (6300): 669–673. Bibcode:2016Sci...353..669P. doi:10.1126/science.aaf2468. hdl:10316/80061. PMID 27516595. S2CID 206647315.
43. Pohl R, et al. (16 September 2016b) "Proton-radius puzzle deepens". *CERN Courier*. After our first study came out in 2010, I was afraid some veteran physicist would get in touch with us and point out our great blunder. But the years have passed, and so far nothing of the kind has happened.
44. Dahia, F; Lemos, A.S. (2016). "Is the proton radius puzzle evidence of extra dimensions?". *European Physical Journal*. 76: 435. arXiv:1509.08735. Bibcode:2016EPJC...76..435D. doi:10.1140/epjc/s10052-016-4266-7. S2CID 118672005
45. Liu Y, McKeen D, Miller GA (2016). "Electrophobic Scalar Boson and Muonic Puzzles". *Physical Review Letters*.

Cite this article: Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich) (2023) Empirical Validation of the "G-d's Physics' Critical Prediction Resolves the "Gravitational Enigma"! . *Research & Reviews Journal of Modern Physics*, "G-D'S PHYSICS" NEW TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY SCIENTIFIC PARADIGM **Special Issue:** 1-5.

Copyright: ©2023 Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich). This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.